

Proceedings of FabLearn Netherlands 2018

Maker education in the Netherlands –
state of play and lessons for the future

Introduction

FabLearn Netherlands invited submissions to the first FabLearn conference in the Netherlands that was held September 28, 2018, preceding Maker Faire Eindhoven September 29 and 30. This publication contains the accepted papers that were presented at the conference.

FabLearn Netherlands brought together national and international researchers, educators, designers, and makers to discuss and explore designing and making in educational contexts, digital fabrication in education, and hands-on learning for the 21st Century.

Some of the main guiding principles of the FabLearn community are the democratization of maker education, its implementation in public education systems, and a focus on constructionist learning. Submissions from both maker education and design and technology education were received.

The FabLearn Netherlands call for papers was organised jointly by Maker-Education.nl, Rotterdam University of Applied Sciences, TU Delft and Waag. FabLearn the Netherlands is a sister conference to the global FabLearn conference that has been held over the past five years at Stanford University, USA.

The state of play of Maker education in the Netherlands - introduction to the research papers

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Figure 1. Girl with her penguin. Picture by Miroslava Silva Ordaz.

We are proud to organize the first FabLearn conference in the Netherlands where many maker education initiatives are shared in masterclasses and on a fair. As early as 2007, the first maker initiatives started in the Netherlands and making keeps gaining momentum in education. As new parties are embracing maker education – its teaching principles as well as the innovative making technologies – it is a good moment to make up a balance of what has been achieved so far and to discuss where maker education could go. The research papers enable us to systematically reflect on the Dutch makers education experiences.

The six papers brought together at the FabLearn Netherlands 2018 conference give a broad picture of maker education in the Netherlands. Some are written by insiders of the maker movement and others are written from the perspective of design and technology education. In this tradition, making and prototyping is seen as a crucial element and vital to the learning of young people. For a complete picture, contributions from arts education are necessary as well, however, research in this area is still scarce. The papers describe various maker initiatives in primary, secondary and higher education and in libraries, however, many of them describe initiatives in primary education. Each paper has its own focus, and together they show what has been achieved in maker

education in the Netherlands, and they highlight issues and new approaches that will forward learning through making in an even better way than before.

Make (almost) anything

The papers all stress that maker education is not just about the new innovative technologies that are used. Surely, they are an important element of the movement as they made it possible to design and build smart and useful products in a way that was not possible before. While these innovative technologies evoked a revival in making, they are usually used alongside simple materials such as carton, duct tape, wood and textiles that are equally valuable in the toolkit of the maker. All these tools together help to “make (almost) anything”.

Key didactic principles: creation, iteration, sharing, and autonomy

All papers show that both learners and their teachers play important and new roles in maker education. Sharing is considered essential in making. How this is organized and facilitated by the “space” or lab is central in the articles by Peter Troxler and Manon Mostert – van der Sar on the FabLab at Rotterdam University of Applied Sciences and by Pierre Gorissen on the iXSpace in Arnhem, a Fablab for (prospective) primary school teachers and their pupils. There are key didactic principles guiding these spaces.

The initiators of the FabLab in Rotterdam show how peer learning, structured assignments, jamming and just-in-time teaching functioned in their lab. They describe how the project-based approach – starting small and building your own smart product through iterations – as a new didactic approach influenced other courses at the University. Also new initiatives such as those in the libraries and the iXspace for those involved in primary education highlight freedom for the learners and creating a maker culture. The function of the space – the stewards and the equipment – is to create a culture of innovation and trust and to create what is called a “maker mindset”. The paper by Emer Beamer and Dylan Heather on the Designathon approach shows how this is done in workshops for primary school pupils in the Netherlands and elsewhere. Successes are described, talents discovered and students pursuing making in their careers.

The right kind of conflict to foster a Maker mindset

The papers are not just about successes, it is noted that learners (both students and teachers) drop out or encounter great difficulties, despite the maker movement promoting the slogan “Everybody is a Maker” and celebration of the maker mindset. This maker mindset is related to self-efficacy, motivation and interest. However, almost all papers signal that in practice this maker mindset is not always there. University students drop out during minors and primary school teachers do not feel competent as makers nor as facilitators of making. Pierre Gorissen warns that bringing devices and equipment to schools is not enough, risks surround maker education, especially as it gets momentum, and Annemarie Looijenga notices frustration and passiveness amongst pupils during making in design and technology education. It is important to realize that people are not born as makers and that there are

dangers in the open approach of the makers education. Certainly, many pupils regain motivation because they are able to make things that are of personal interest. And yes, spontaneous peer-to-peer support while waiting for a machine eased by the informal culture is valuable. And yes, it is a positive thing to let learners deal with uncertainties and to have them iterate, this is indeed a strong element of maker education. However, a task may become too overwhelming and not doable for learners resulting in anxiety.

New answers start to come to the surface. Annemarie Looijenga argues that tasks need to be bordered to evoke the discovery behavior and the tinkering that is needed to arrive at new artefacts and insights. Making tasks must not become frustrating and put the learner in discomfort nor should these tasks be without any cognitive conflict. Learners need some cognitive conflict and to reconsider some of their ideas – a certain challenge is essential – but learners also have to perceive a task as doable. When this is not the case, they will become passive and frustrated. This insight is transferable to other educational contexts as well and might function as a lens to study how learners function in maker spaces and elsewhere. In fact, when Peter Troxler and Manon Mostert – van der Sar advise their students to start with something small when building their own smart product, this is about creating the right kind of cognitive conflict.

Peer to peer support

A strong element of maker education are the peers that are there to support each other. This is different from traditional education where – putting it bluntly – the teacher is the only supporter and expert. In maker education, peers maybe even more knowledgeable than stewards or teachers, and the line between them is blurred as they learn alongside. This requires new attitudes and competences from teachers. There is a substantial body of research (Slavin, Hurley & Chamberlain 2003) that demonstrates the extraordinary power of collaborative and cooperative learning, maker education has developed effective practices to do so. The layout of maker spaces – e.g. the free movement in the ISpace lab – and the stewards and teachers – are important. And supposedly even elements like being open during non-office hours and having a specific place on campus creates the spirit of peer-to-peer support.

Formative evaluation

Quite a number of papers address the issue of formative evaluation. A lot is learned during making. However, when the learners know where they are going and reflect on their process and their skills, more can be learned. Tom Van Eijck at the University of Applied Science in Amsterdam and his colleagues started to work with learning reports. Children filled in learning reports at the end of an afternoon in the maker space. These reports focused on some of the core learning goals in maker education such as creativity and peer-to-peer support. They showed where learners stood in the learning process and could be used to see how to proceed. Remke Klapwijk and Nadine Rodewijk are on the same page of clarifying prototyping goals through a fun to play game – in the context of open design assignments. Annemarie Looijenga repeatedly shows the need for evaluation during design and making tasks as a way to

activate pupils and adapt the challenge to the learner.

Making, Designing and Changing

It is a pleasure to notice that people from various backgrounds are visiting FabLearn and love to hear about the discoveries done by innovative teachers – and a bunch of researchers in the background – systematically observing and describing what is done and trying to explain successes and failures. All authors, implicit or explicit, merge insights from the maker movement with insights from design and technology education as well as general educational research.

The articles brought together at FabLearn Netherlands 2018 can be read as a joint evaluation of the work until now. The insights in formative evaluation are an expression of the principles of peer support and sharing of maker education and are promising for the future of maker education. The contributions can also be seen as collective endeavor to get a clearer direction and ideas for the next step: How can this sort of togetherness be created and kept alive when labs become more mainstream? How can this be realized in classrooms and libraries? Or in a maker space for primary education? How can more teachers be encouraged and enabled to adopt maker education into their repertoire of teaching practices? How can making become a meaningful approach that contributes to achieving the core objectives of primary, secondary and higher education?

We warmly invite you to read the various contributions, to get inspiration for ~~your own practice, and to get involved in the debate.~~

Slavin, R.E., E.A. Hurley and A. Chamberlain, 2003. Cooperative learning and achievement: In: W.M. Reynolds & G.J. Miller (Eds), Handbook of Psychology; Educational Psychology, Vol. 7, Hoboken, NJ: Wiley, pp. 177-198.

Colophon

Program Committee

Papers were reviewed by:

- Peter Troxler, Rotterdam University of Applied Sciences, chair
- Remke Klapwijk, Delft University of Technology, Science, Education and Communication, co-chair
- Monique Pijls, Amsterdam University of Applied Sciences
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FabLearn call for papers was organized by:

- Karien Vermeulen, Waag
- Alicja Żenczykowska, on behalf of FabLearn

Publication websites

These papers are published at:

FabLearn: www.fablearn.org

Maker Education: www.makereducation.nl

Rotterdam University of Applied Sciences: www.hogeschoolrotterdam.nl

Waag: www.waag.org

TU Delft: www.wetenschapsknooppuntzh.nl

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